

Relevance of Guidance and Counselling Services in School Life

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Received : 01/09/2023

1st BPR : 05/09/2023

2nd BPR : 13/09/2023

Accepted : 22/09/2023

Abstract

This research paper explores the vital role of guidance and counselling services in the lives of students within the school environment. It discusses the multifaceted challenges students face in contemporary educational settings and underscores the importance of effective guidance and counselling programs in addressing these challenges. Through a comprehensive review of literature and empirical evidence, this article demonstrates how guidance and counselling services contribute to the holistic development, well-being, and academic success of students. It also highlights emerging trends and best practices in the field, providing insights for educators, policymakers, and practitioners on optimizing these services for the benefit of students.

Keywords: Guidance, Counselling Service, Development, Student, Adolescence and Adjustment.

Introduction

Knowledge of the goal is very important for the success of any work. Guidance is the help that is given by one person to another person in making choices, making adjustments and solving problems. The main objective of guidance is to provide such help to every person that he/she can gain knowledge of his abilities and powers and by developing these abilities and powers, he/she can establish their relation with life values and life objectives and ultimately become capable of So that he can show his own path. It is not limited only to school or family, but it extends to every aspect of life, be it home, family, business, industry, social life, hospital, prison or the proper use of leisure moments.

In ancient times, when any person living in the society faced any kind of problem, he used to seek advice from the head of the family or the head of the community and thus through guidance and counselling help by the head of the family or the head of the community. Used to get solution to his problem. Although this solution was not systematic and scientific, it solved the problem immediately and put an end to the person's problem. With the passage of time, this process of consultation also gradually changed. After the origin of the state, the important role of the minister was established as the advisor to the king and thus after receiving guidance, the king started solving the disputes and problems related to his state. In today's perspective, as a result of changes in various fields, the help of practically trained persons is required to guide the individual. The need for guidance and counselling services to adjust to the environment, adapt and prepare oneself for future conditions and develop personal capabilities has increased a lot in today's era because it is related to all aspects of life.

If the need for guidance and counselling services is being felt the most in the present times, it is in schools. If we truly want to benefit from guidance and counselling services, then guidance and counselling services should start from the primary school level itself. For this, teachers and non-teaching staff who are related to these tasks should be given adequate training so that they can give proper guidance and advice to the children or encourage them to follow the right path and also remove

the obstacles coming in this path. At the primary level, there are many children whose homes do not have enough money to arrange for food and send the children to school or the child does not have enough time to go to school. Even if the student comes to school, he keeps failing in the same class several times due to lack of proper teaching. Many times, inappropriate curriculum, incompetent teachers, lack of facilities in the school, etc. also promote wastage and obstruction. In such a situation, the role of guidance and counselling services becomes more essential.

By using guidance and counselling services at the primary level, we can identify special children. After identifying them, their teaching work can be accelerated by making arrangements for education according to their physical and mental condition. At this stage, children's interest in studies can be increased by taking the help of guidance and counselling services in their educational work and making proper use of positive and negative reinforcement related to their response. To develop good habits, to identify and develop interests and aptitudes, to develop healthy study habits, to develop the spirit of cooperation and collaboration, to participate in sports and other recreational programs and to utilize leisure time. Guidance and counselling services can be used to make good use of and develop interest in extra-curricular and co-curricular activities.

Just as the shape and form that a potter gives to a pot while making it, the same form and shape remains till the pot is destroyed. Similarly, if all the virtues are developed in the child at the primary level by using guidance and counselling services, then the child will cherish these qualities throughout his life.

Therefore, maximum use of guidance and counselling services at the primary level should be ensured to ensure the development of the above mentioned qualities in the child. At the middle school level, students are in the stage of pre-adolescence. At this level, students can be used to suggest problems related to social action through guidance and counselling services, develop leadership qualities and learn any work by working together in a group and inspired by the collective spirit. Along with this, guidance is provided in discovering and diagnosing the reasons hindering the physical, mental and emotional progress of the students, leading a disciplined life, developing healthy habits, developing the right attitude towards life and making good use of leisure time. Counselling services can be used. At the high school level, students reach adolescence. During adolescence they have to face many types of problems. Due to rapid physical changes, many types of problems arise in them which they are unaware of it. Adolescence is a transitional period between childhood and adulthood which is commonly referred to as a state of stress and storm for many reasons.

With sexual maturity in adolescence, inclination towards sex-related topics increases. Teenagers have more aggressive tendencies and lack foresight. In this stage, adolescents want to achieve a special status in their peer group and by maintaining it, they are eager to gain prestige in the eyes of parents and teachers. Independence is a major need of teenagers during adolescence. They prefer to sleep, read, write and live in a separate room in the house so that They can properly direct his thoughts and thinking. They want to live his life in his own way. Even they don't like if their parents come to school and get details of their educational achievements and inquire about the school manager/principal in this regard because they consider it childish and it hurts their sense of independence. The peak of the need and need for independence is seen in adolescents when they become ready to stand on their own feet. In adolescence a person feels the need to set a clear philosophy of life for himself/herself.

He also starts pondering over various questions about truth, religion and ideals. The tendency for religious change and participation in any movement is most intense during adolescence. Therefore, the role of guidance and counselling services becomes important to establish adjustment in the physical, mental, social, political, economic and educational changes taking place in adolescents during adolescence. By using guidance and counselling services in adolescence, problems related to adjustment in school, problems related to family relations and social adjustment, problems related to moral behaviour, problems related to professional adjustment, financial problems, problem of drug abuse and problem of suicide can be solved. Diagnosis can be made. During adolescence, help of guidance and counselling services can be taken in planning and developing interest in entertainment interests, social interests, personal interests, educational interests, professional interests, religious

interests and interest in status symbols among teenagers. During adolescence, sexual organs of teenagers attain maturity. Therefore, this stage is very important from sexual point of view. In sexual context, adolescent boys and girls should be made aware of all the facts related to sexual topics, sexual distortions and ill effects through individual and group guidance services and should develop a healthy attitude towards sex.

In India, there is a system of elections in some subjects mostly from the secondary level itself. In higher secondary classes, there should be arrangements for proper guidance and counselling services so that students can choose the right field according to their circumstances and ability from among the options like Arts, Science and Commerce, Agriculture etc. Initially, when students take admission in a new school, they have to face difficulties related to admission. Also, there is a need for adjustment between new friends and teachers. The school environment and curriculum are new. Therefore, guidance and counselling services play an important role in adjusting in these circumstances.

At the university and college level, most of the students have passed or are about to pass adolescence. If the students have got the benefit of proper guidance and counselling services at the middle school and high school level, then they do not face much trouble at the university and college level and they solve most of their problems very easily, yet it is often seen that It is known that at this stage some new problems arise for which students require guidance and counselling services. Due to being deprived of guidance and counselling services, the students at the university level become misguided and resort to theft, robbery, pickpocketing, and the extreme of this is seen when the students at this level get involved in acts like murder and rape. In such a situation, use of guidance and counselling services becomes extremely necessary.

By using these services, on one hand we make the students aware of the ill effects of these wrong actions and develop a positive attitude towards them, but also motivate them to stop doing such things. At this stage most of the students enter into married life which on one hand brings them happiness and on the other hand brings many problems. We can solve these problems through guidance and counselling services. At this stage students are worried about the profession they will adopt in the future. Through the use of guidance and counselling services, students can be provided comprehensive business-related information regarding various opportunities and work areas existing in the society. Apart from this, they should be given information about training for higher positions and competitions

held at national and international level through professional guidance. Guidance and counselling services are a lifelong process because other problems go on simultaneously in life.

Whenever any problem arises in life, guidance and counselling services are required. Even after finding a solution to the problem, many other problems related to it continue to arise. As a result, there is a constant need for guidance and counselling services. By using guidance and counselling services, we can ensure overall development of personality by developing the quality of adjustment among the students in school life. Also, students can take the help of guidance and counselling services to understand their life goals intelligently and to understand the obstacles coming in the way of achieving life goals and to solve them appropriately.

Conclusion

This research paper emphasizes the ongoing relevance of guidance and counselling services in school life. By addressing the multifaceted challenges students encounter, these services contribute significantly to students' personal development, mental well-being, academic success, and career readiness. As schools continue to evolve, it is imperative to prioritize and invest in high-quality guidance and counselling programs to support the holistic growth and flourishing of students in the 21st century. *The New Education Policy (NEP) of 2020 in India places significant emphasis on guidance and counselling as an integral part of the education system. The policy recognizes the importance of nurturing the holistic development of students and providing them with the necessary support to make informed decisions about their education and future careers.*

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